

Overview of use cases.

ID	Description	Use-Case Archtype	Business Outcome	Industry	Business Function
GLR					
S1	Chat with own documents	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S2	Automated response to status inquiries (Email or Call-Center)	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Financial Services	Marketing and after-sales services
S3	Finance Risk Assessment	Analysis	Decision Support & Analysis	Financial Services	Management
S4	Search internal documents context-based retrieval	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S5	Information retrieval (Chatbot)	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Sales
S6	Handling internal and external inquiries (Chatbot)	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S7	Chat with documents employment regulations and employee benefits	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S8	Internal Chatbot (Google Cloud RAG)	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S9	Real-time information about competitors (current offerings) during customer conversations	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Consumer & Media	Sales
S10	Vectorization of existing API enabling automatic creation of new APIs that follow format	Software & Query Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Consumer & Media	Information and communications technology
S11	Enhances delivery support with chatbot (Dasher problems/questions)	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Consumer & Media	Administrative and back-office tasks
S12	Customer Service question answering	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S13	Internal policies chatbot	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S14	AI faculty chatbot helping teach entrepreneurship course	Knowledge Transfer & Education	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Other services not included elsewhere
S15	Conversation with videos chatbot that can summarize video content	Summary & Report Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Other services not included elsewhere
S16	Report generation and Fraud investigation	Analysis	Decision Support & Analysis	Financial Services	Management
S17	Provide support executives with accurate, up-to-date responses while maintaining conversational interaction	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Consumer & Media	Marketing and after-sales services
S18	Text-to-SQL prompt helping users to select the relevant data sources	Software & Query Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology
S19	Improve customer classification and migrate to standardized classification system	Analysis	Decision Support & Analysis	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S20	Locating internal Policies	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S21	Corporate data chatbot	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Industrials & Manufacturing	Administrative and back-office tasks
S22	Document process automation (pipeline)	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Industrials & Manufacturing	Administrative and back-office tasks
S23	Better search and search summarization	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S24	Chat with documents for bank internal documents	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S25	Summarization and data retrieval procedures on data about China's political economy	Summary & Report Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Financial Services	Management
S26	"Step suggerter" to assist students in cybersecurity coursework	Knowledge Transfer & Education	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Other services not included elsewhere
S27	AI chatbot to retrieve information on gun safety	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Industrials & Manufacturing	Administrative and back-office tasks
S28	AI4Legal internal and legal documents query for preparation of legal opinions	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S29	AI4Content text generation with brand guidelines	Content Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S30	AI4E-learning personalized learning and employee development	Knowledge Transfer & Education	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S31	AI4Knowledge Base internal document search and information retrieval	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S32	AI4Localisation automating translation and localization processes	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks

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ID	Description	Use-Case Archtype	Business Outcome	Industry	Business Function
S33	interactive chatbot for finding answers in documents	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S34	AI-powered search and natural language data querying	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Other services not included elsewhere
S35	Chatbot focused on lung health	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Healthcare	Other services not included elsewhere
S36	Retrieve and summarize clinical data to support diagnostics decisions	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Healthcare	Other services not included elsewhere
S37	Automatic form filling for Requests for Proposals	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Sales
S38	Automatic form filling for Requests for In-formation	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Sales
S39	Customer Support Chatbot	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Consumer & Media	Marketing and after-sales services
S40	Document Summarization and Search	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S41	Recommend treatment and support medical diagnostics	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Healthcare	Other services not included elsewhere
S42	Personalized Learning and Tutoring System	Knowledge Transfer & Education	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Other services not included elsewhere
S43	Fraud detection system (with RAG in pipeline)	Analysis	Decision Support & Analysis	Financial Services	Management
S44	AI-driven recommendation engine	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Consumer & Media	Sales
S45	Internal document search enterprise knowledge management	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S46	Q&A answering (whit link reference)	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Healthcare	Administrative and back-office tasks
S47	Support tool for customer support teams	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Marketing and after-sales services
S48	Voice scam detection	Analysis	Decision Support & Analysis	Financial Services	Management
S49	Automated processing of investment data (emails and attachments)	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S50	Enterprise search engine (internal)	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Marketing and after-sales services
S51	Provide highly-personalized lead recommendations	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Technology & Telecommunications	Sales
S52	Help employees prepare for their upcoming interviews	Knowledge Transfer & Education	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Management
S53	Sales Intelligence Analyst	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Technology & Telecommunications	Sales
S54	Employee HR question answering	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Management
S55	Summarize financial metrics	Summary & Report Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Management
S56	Code generation	Software & Query Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology
S57	Smarter ticket resolution	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S58	Automatically fill out proposal and request forms	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Sales
S59	Email draft and templating	Content Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology
S60	SEO optimized content creation	Content Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S61	HR candidate pulling	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S62	Personalized marketing campaigns	Content Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S63	Optimize logistic planning based on real-time data	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Industrials & Manufacturing	Management
S64	Retrieving legal cases / decisions	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S65	Personalized learning	Knowledge Transfer & Education	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Other services not included elsewhere
S66	Better planning projects by incorporating historical data reports and forecasting timelines	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Technology & Telecommunications	Management
S67	Summarize meetings with key points	Summary & Report Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Management
S68	Internal Data Retrieval	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Administrative and back-office tasks
S69	Customer chatbot for related offerings, account issues and troubleshooting	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Consumer & Media	Marketing and after-sales services
S70	Clinical decision support and doctor assisting	Decision Support	Decision Support & Analysis	Healthcare	Other services not included elsewhere
S71	Data retrieval for financial consultants	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Administrative and back-office tasks
S72	Assistant for customers and internal teams optimizing service delivery and operational speed	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Marketing and after-sales services
S73	Access patents, scientific literature and market intelligence	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Other services not included elsewhere

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S74	Context-Aware conversational agents	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services
S75	Real-time event commentary	Content Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Consumer & Media	Other services not included elsewhere
S76	Intelligent Content & Asset Creation	Content Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing and after-sales services

Interviews

A	Search Assistant for Support	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology
B	Medical QA	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Healthcare	Other Services
C	Chatbot for Customer with ChatOps	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing & After-sales
D	Chat Assistant with Specific Expertise	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Financial Services	Admin & Back-office
E	Find Information from Repository	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology
F	Search Assistant for Different Tools	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Professional Services	Information and communications technology
G	Modular RAG System for Companies	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Admin & Back-office
H	Get Information About Other Employees/Team Group Messages	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Admin & Back-office
I	QA for Ticketing System	Internal Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing & After-sales
J	Automatic Customer Support	External Knowledge Assistant	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Marketing & After-sales
K	Contract Formatting	Summary & Report Generation	Content & Asset Creation	Technology & Telecommunications	Other Services
L	Search Documentation	Document Retrieval	Knowledge Retrieval & Engagement	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology
M	Automation of Legacy Systems	Process & Workflow Automation	Process & Workflow Automation	Technology & Telecommunications	Information and communications technology